

IS MINING REALLY BENEFICIAL? VALUING THE POSSIBLE EFFECTS OF MINING TO HUMAN HEALTH, CULTURE AND INDIGENOUS SOCIO-ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES

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ABSTRACT

Responsible mining is the term often brandished by large scale mining companies in the world. For indigenous people who belong to the most marginalized and vulnerable sectors of society, large-scale mining often leads to the loss of their lands and livelihood and thus poses a serious threat to their health and culture. The imminent mining operation in the mountain of Villa Cerveza in Victoria, Oriental Mindoro, Philippines brought fear among the Mangyans because it affects the strong cultural ties of indigenous community leading to loss of their culture and identity. Economic value cannot fully envisage cultural value for there are specific attributes of cultural value, particularly the social aspects, which cannot be reduced to tantamount a monetary form. Valuing the cost of health in mining communities is also presented here. The 'environmental burden of disease' continuously grows from time to time due to inherent major factors of risks in water and air issues. However, considering the mining-related health risk to the proximal communities, a rise on the morbidity rate is expected. This study employed total economic valuation (TEV) approach to provide estimates of the mining impacts to human health and welfare, culture, and socio-economic activities. The result serves as basis for the decision making to arrive at a win-win solution for communal benefits.

Keywords: mangyan, indigenous people, culture, identity, economic value

INTRODUCTION

The mining industry is a major force in the world economy, occupying a primary position at the start of the resource supply chain (ICMM, 2012). In the Philippines alone, the contention flows along mining's environmental costs against its real contribution to the national economy. An estimated \$840 billion worth of unutilized mineral resources could be found in the country according to the Mines and Geosciences Bureau of the Philippines which attracts investors and serves as dictating factor for the issuance of exploration permits to mining companies (Espiritu, 2015).

Roubini (2013), one of the world's renowned economists stressed out that mining sector will be an important source of economic growth for the Philippines in the future along with tourism. In the last four months of 2012, the mining and quarrying sector contributed a mere 0.2% to the overall economy, bringing the overall impact of the sector to the GDP to a 0.1% contraction. Nickel mining was the biggest contributor to the sector with a growth of 33.5% as compared with the 2012 total contribution falling only at 7.7%. What brings great concern here is the worse impact of large scale mining projects not only to the environment but to health, culture and indigenous socio-economic activities.

This study generally aims to value in monetary terms the effect of the proposed Mindoro Nickel Project to human health, culture and indigenous socio-economic activities and eventually suggest policy recommendations for that purpose. Specifically, this paper will: 1) Analyze and evaluate the probable effects of large scale mining to human health in communities which are expected to receive direct impacts of mining operations; 2) Value in terms of willingness to pay (government spending) the effects of mining to Mangyans' culture and heritage; and 3) Analyze and evaluate the possible effects of large scale mining to indigenous socio-economic activities of the Mangyans.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study, aside from the use of exploratory and logically inductive qualitative method, employed total economic valuation (TEV) to provide estimates of the mining impacts to human health and welfare, culture, and socio-economic activities.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Possible Mining Effects to Human Health

Morbidity rate is the proportion of patients with a particular disease during a given year per given unit of population (*The American Heritage Stedman's Medical Dictionary*, 2002). In 2010, the Municipality of Victoria, reached a population of 43, 308 with a growth rate of 1.80% from 1990 to 2010 (NSO, 1990, 2000, 2010) while the Municipality of Pola has 32, 984 (*Municipality of Pola Socio-Economic and Physical Profile*, 2011).

In a year, the incidence of common diseases increases by 10% (Burnett et al, 1997). However, considering the mining-related health risk to the proximal communities, a rise on the morbidity rate is expected. The incidence or prevalence of diseases in that case will not be merely common types because of nickel and other metal induced toxicity and carcinogenicity (Das, Das and Dhundasi, 2008).

While most of the diseases are commonly caused by bacteria and virus, the cost of morbidity is computed through Expenses on Healthcare per Household based on Household Final Consumption Expenditure, 2nd Quarter of 2013 and 2nd Quarter of 2014 at current prices, in million pesos over an average household size of 5 members.

The World Health Organization (WHO) between 2002 and 2004 included the environmental and occupational factors among the indicators of risk factors for health and has provided a method to calculate it based on an exposure approach (WHO 2002b, 2004). The term adapted is "environmental burden of disease". In 2007, WHO released its first ever country-by-country analysis of the impacts environmental factors has on health for its 192 member-nations (WHO, 2009a) which include the Philippines. These estimates assist countries in policy and decision-making procedures for health and environment sectors leading to setting up of priorities for preventive action (ibid).

Philippines environmental burden of disease for selected risk factors falls at 20% in 2009 (Fewtrell et al., 2007; Desai et al., 2004; Smith et al.,2004; Ostro, 2004; Cohen, et al., 2004). Major factors of health risks include water and air issues. The same factors that would induce further health risks during mining operations. The same percentage was used to compute for the cost of diseases in the municipalities that would be directly affected by mining operations.

Victoria which is the seat municipality of the mining site is expected to have an estimated total cost of diseases amounting to Php 402, 270, 643.35 for 25 years of mining operation considering the nine primary causes of morbidity which include acute respiratory infection, pneumonia, bronchitis, hypertension, diarrhea, influenza, urinary tract infection, respiratory tuberculosis and diseases of the heart.

Pola, where the plant site is to be located has an estimated total cost of diseases amounting to Php 1,190,044,533.46 for 25 years with registered 10 causes of morbidity which include acute respiratory infection, urinary tract infection, upper respiratory tract infection, pneumonia, various forms of wounds, diarrhea, pulmonary tuberculosis, peptic ulcer disease, acute tonsillopharyngitis, and hypertension.

The Cost of Mangyans' Culture and Heritage

Economic value cannot fully envisage cultural value for there are specific attributes of cultural value, particularly the social aspects, which cannot be reduced to tantamount a monetary form. There is a work on cultural valuation that transcends to what economic value is capable of capturing (Klamer, 2002 & 2004). For instance the value of national identity, expressed as a feeling of 'Britishness' or 'Frenchness' (Throsby, 2006) will be very difficult for individuals to express in any monetary form as they are rooted in shared social experiences, rather than individual utility. The same fact is also attributed to being a 'Filipino' or a 'Mangyan'.

Equally there are benefits which conceptually resist monetization, the afore-cited example being trust - it fundamentally misunderstands the meaning of trust if one can put a monetary valuation on it (Arrow, 2010b). There is a belief that there are intrinsic qualities in an object that cannot be understood using the framework of economic valuation (Throsby, 2001 and Holden, 2004 & 2006). Throsby suggests the need for some form of cultural assessment for decision-making, although he is not clear

on the criteria to base this judgment on. Nonetheless an 'independent assessment of cultural value will always be important in informing decision-making in regard to heritage, no matter how thorough an economic assessment is made' (2006:43).

The method employed here to value Mangyan heritage and culture is the national government expenditure for the conservation, promotion and protection of culture and the arts. It is deemed here as the willingness to pay (WTP).

In 2014, the Philippine Government through the National Commission for Culture and the Arts (NCCA) has allotted Php 27,280,000.00 as regional allocation (http://www.dbm.gov.ph/?page_id=6697, downloaded on April 29, 2015). Considering that Region IV-B MIMAROPA is composed of five provinces, each may have received Php 5,456,000.00 during the year.

The Possible Effects of Mining to Indigenous Socio-Economic Activities of the Mangyans

The proposed exploration/mining site is the haven for the Alangan and Tadyawan Mangyan tribes of Mindoro, which are the directly affected indigenous people. Their economic and social activities are inseparable. They have inherent and unique culture and traditions. Nature is the binding element of their traditional way of life. They are dependent on the available resources around them. In their traditional society, what is generally practiced is the subsistence agricultural economy, wherein households normally produce only for what they need for their day-to-day food consumption (Gariguez, 2008).

Their major means of subsistence include hunting/trapping, fishing, farming, charcoal production, gathering of forest products and handicrafts. They hunt and trap wild pigs, birds, frogs, monitor lizards and snakes for their household consumption. They catch fishes in the Mag-asawang Tubig, Ibulo and Aglubang Rivers by net or by use of Derris roots (tubli). Particular species called *pait* or *paitan*, goby (*biya*) and freshwater shrimp are endemic in the area. Fish catch is relatively rare in volume and practically sold at Php 30.00 per kilogram.

They practice swidden farming (kaingin). They plant rice, sweet potato, taro, banana, vegetables, ginger and fruit trees in the cleared lands for their own economic utility. They also raise chicken and pigs in their backyards.

Aside from charcoal making from forest woods, they gather forest products such as edible fern (pako), wild yam (nami), buri, rattan, betel nut, buyo, orchids, buho (bamboo), honey, cogon (roofing material), herbal medicines (leaves, roots and tree barks). Some of these are food staples while others are being used as raw material for the production of woven textiles, rattan baskets, *nito* baskets and beaded items.

Household members are committed to a variety of livelihood activities, basically the father and mother assume the entire burden of food sourcing. They consume their own agricultural produce and trade the excess for money which they later spend to acquire their basic family needs. They also sell handicrafts as an additional source of income. These endemic forest by-products are disposed directly to local market or to transient buyers.

Given the fact that a Mangyan household can produce hard goods for sale, there would be an estimated earning amounting to Php 9,370.00 in a month or a total estimated yearly earning amounting to Php 112,440.00 provided that all raw materials needed are available throughout the production cycle. Actualities of quantity and price of individual handicraft were supplied by a transient buyer from lowland Villa Cerveza. This shows how they could earn in a month or a year by utilizing native or endemic forest products and not the individual or household income *per se*.

Tangibly and intangibly, forests contribute in all aspects of culture including language, history, art, religion, medicine, and even social structure itself. It may host the spirits of dead ancestors as well as those of the living and at the same time, viewed as possessing either positive and negative sources of good and evil powers that may induce or impede development. The mystical qualities of specific forest resources often play a crucial role in traditional healing practices. Forests provide the venue for religious, social, and healing ceremonies. There are specific forest products that are useful for their

ceremonies. For Mangyans, forests provide the venue for many cultural events and everything in there are protected and valued for particular cultural occasions and as historic symbols (FAO, 2012).

Table 1. A Resume of Tangible and Intangible Benefits of Forest among *Mangyans*

TANGIBLE AND INTANGIBLE BENEFITS	RATIONALE
Medicine forest / therapeutic mountain	Mangyan health and healing belief are rooted with nature throughout their lives. Their popular healing practices are <i>hilot</i> (therapeutic massage), <i>tapal</i> (poultice), and <i>pagmamaraw</i> (traditional faith healing). They depend on plants and trees from which they gather leaves, roots and barks to treat diseases (ethno pharmacy).
Livelihood	For Mangyan, nature and land is life and without it means death and vanity. They depend solely on forest, rivers and their swidden farms as mainstream livelihood.
Spiritual space and sacred ground	Ancestral lands are not fundamentally deemed as source of living for the Mangyans but also provide them interface with their gods: Kapwan Bulod – god that protects the mountains and forests Alubaba – protector of rivers Bakwel – protector of plants and swidden farms They have also a spiritual practice of festivity during harvesting period called “ <i>Agpamago</i> ”. Burial sites in <i>Alyanay</i> <i>Buwisan</i> where the tribe elders conduct yearly rituals <i>Puting Bato</i> , pangisdaan/sakahan where they hunt and gather foods and other materials

The practice of swidden farming among Alangan Mangyans consists of eleven stages. Two of which and popular are firebreak-making (*Agait*) and fallowing (*Agpagamas*). A firebreak prevents fire during burning to go beyond the swidden site. Two years after clearing, cultivation of the swidden is normally ceased and the site is allowed to revert back to forest (Quiaoit, 1997).

For the indigenous peoples, the entirety of the land is *life* which means it is not just a bare source of livelihood. The broad sense of the term *land* is strongly associated with *home* that refers to a traditional territorial claim and an identity as a community with socio-cultural values closely linked to the environment (Binodngan Ancestral Domains, 2011). This is a reality among Mangyans.

In the past, lands are considered as communal among Alangan Mangyans. They believe that lands should not be owned privately and be a source of greediness but rather an endowment of the community. The Alangan Mangyans have core belief that lands are owned by their God (www.ccsenet.org/jsd, 2012. Accessed March 15, 2015).

Village leaders or the council of elders act as guardians of values and practices and are in charge of ensuring the “protection of watersheds, water sources, and acceptable uses of forests and resources” (Binodngan Ancestral Domains, 2011).

Some large mining companies in the Philippines often brandish the banner that there is life in mining and at the same time values the environment and community through responsible mining (Hilomen-Velasco, 2011). For indigenous peoples, however, who belong to the most marginalised and vulnerable sectors of society, large-scale mining often leads to the loss of their lands and thus poses a serious threat to their livelihoods. Noticeably, about 60 percent of mining operations in the Philippines take place in ancestral domains and often without the consent of the affected communities, which eventually fall victim to displacement and numerous human rights violations including arbitrary

detention, persecution, killings of community representatives, demolition of houses, destruction of property, and similar atrocities (Baguilat, 2011). The imminent mining operation in the mountain of Villa Cerveza brought fear among the Mangyans because it affects the strong cultural ties of indigenous communities leading to loss of their culture and identity (ibid).

Table 2. A Resume of Effects of the Imminent Mining to Mangyans' Culture, Social Life and Intrinsic Economic Activities

ETIC AND EMIC STANDPOINT	RATIONALE
Destruction of natural resources	Means exploitation of land, forest, trees and minerals for the benefits of the few Loss of traditional source of livelihood (hunting grounds, swidden farms and scarcity of honey) Loss of the culture of <i>agpansula</i> (ritual of sacrificing an animal, i.e. chicken or pig), <i>pagmamaraw</i> or traditional faith healing, traditional clothing, and arranged marriage tradition.
Annihilation of cultural heritage	Deprivation of sacred places/grounds for their rituals, prayers, ethnic practices and burial sites. For them, when burial sites are disturbed would mean more deaths among family members. An incident was recorded when these sites were desecrated (Gariguez, 2008).
Displacement	Expulsion from their homeland and traditional way of life. They will lose the chance of sending their children to learn from a government-operated primary school (Grade 1 to 4) situated within lower <i>Kisloyan</i> . The place is part of the exploration site. Their community centers or <i>Balay Lakoy</i> which serve as living quarter for a number of families in one sitio will be displaced.

During the scoping exercise conducted for the mining company in 1999, Dames and Moore Environmental Consultants confirmed that Mangyans sacred places will be directly affected by the project operation. Nevertheless the NCIP was complicit in the conduct of a seriously flawed FPIC process and permits were subsequently issued by the responsible Government agencies. The Mangyan ancestral domain claimants made it clear in statements at the initial stages of exploration in same year that the sacredness of their ancestral domain was the one primary reason for their rejecting the mining project (*Position Paper of Samahang Nagkakaisang Mangyan Alangan*, 1999).

The displacement of settled communities is a significant cause of resentment and conflict associated with large-scale mineral development. Entire communities may be uprooted and forced to shift elsewhere, often into purpose-built settlements not necessarily of their own choosing. Besides losing their homes, communities may also lose their land, and thus their livelihoods. Community institutions and power relations may also be disrupted. Displaced communities are often settled in areas without adequate resources or are left near the mine, where they may bear the brunt of pollution and contamination. Forced resettlement can be particularly disastrous for indigenous communities who have strong cultural and spiritual ties to the lands of their ancestors and who may find it difficult to survive when these are broken (IIED, 2002).

For the 11, 522.88 hectares to be mined, the guaranteed financial assistance for the IPs is Php 15,000.00 per hectare with a total amount of Php 172,843,200.00 for 25 years (INTEX Resources, 2009).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A total estimated amount of PhP 1,772,024,376.81 might be the induced damages of the proposed Mindoro Nickel Project to health, culture, heritage and socio-economic activities for the duration of 25 years operation. Impacts to human health would be aggravated by mining airborne and waterborne risks. This study looked unto the government spending as a measure of the total willingness to pay (WTP) for the preservation of national culture, arts and heritage. The total willingness to accept (WTA) on the part the Mangyans was not accounted but could be included in future studies to arrive at an economically acceptable explanation of the culture and heritage cost. Possible effects to indigenous socio-economic activities are measured in terms of loss of livelihood which is basically dependent on the actual benefits of forest and rivers. The cost of resettlement was also considered in this paper to understand a trade-off.

Mindoro Nickel Project is so alarming considering the effects it may cause to life, society and culture. Health risks in the communities deemed to be affected by the mining operations could be prevented by firm environmental, cultural and social policies. There should be a strong local policy support to The Natural Cultural Heritage Act of 2009 (RA 10066) and The Indigenous Peoples' Rights Act of 1997 (RA 8731). Indigenous cultural community must be defined and protected at all cost. Ancestral domains and ancestral lands must be upheld. The traditional lifestyle of the Mangyans in the mining area is bounded on forest and natural resources. They are present in the area since the time immemorial, thus destructing them or forcing them to relocate would mean separation to their beliefs, culture, customs and natural source of life.

The forest resources within the mining area, which is the provider of major socio-economic activities of the Mangyans, will be destroyed during operation. In consonance with RA 7586 (NIPAS Act of 1992, Section 4 (k) - Strict Nature Reserve) buffer zones must also be established to ensure protection of the forest resources which is the main generator of major socio-economic activities in the area.

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